

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF TREATMENT EFFECTIVENESS FOR DIABETIC RETINOPATHY WITH MACULAR EDEMA IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Relevance. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic systemic disease characterized by the inability of the human body to produce or use sufficient insulin, a hormone that allows cells to absorb glucose from the bloodstream. Research Aim. Comparative assessment of the effectiveness of treatment for diabetic retinopathy with macular edema in patients with diabetes mellitus using various therapy methods.

Purpose: Comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of the treatment of diabetic retinopathy with macular edema in patients with diabetes mellitus using various therapies.

Methods and techniques. The analysis of examination and treatment results of 154 eyes with severe non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy was presented. Of these, 38 eyes comprised the control group, which received laser photocoagulation (LPC) in combination with fenofibrate, and the effect of this treatment was evaluated dynamically over 1 year. The main group of 116 eyes received intravitreal anti-VEGF injections (IAIs) also in combination with fenofibrate, and the effect of this treatment was evaluated over 1 year.

Results: Comparative analysis of the two therapy approaches showed that with timely application of IAIs, the treatment efficacy for macular edema increased by 3.33 times. The criterion of the treatment's reliability was a quantitative analysis of central macular thickness (CMT) before and after LPC and IAIs. If the initial retinal thickness before LPC was 331.2 μm , it decreased to 281.4 μm afterward. The dynamics of edema absorption was 15.04%, whereas in the group receiving IAIs, this indicator was 3.8 times higher, amounting to 57.53%. Our results convincingly demonstrate that anti-VEGF drugs remain the mainstay of therapy for diabetic macular edema. Timely administered IAIs improve best-corrected visual acuity 3.38 times more often and stabilize it 2.74 times more compared to LPC.

Conclusion: The main method of preventing diabetic retinal damage is maximum stable compensation of carbohydrate metabolism, normalization of systolic and diastolic blood pressure indicators, and correction of dyslipidemia with fenofibrate.

References If we are talking about classical macular edema, then angiogenesis inhibitors should be the drug of choice for the first line of therapy in patients with DMO in many cases when the cost and burden of treatment are less limited. Conventional laser therapy will be a secondary intervention in these cases, but will remain a first-line option when the cost and burden of treatment are more limited.

At the same time, the main way to prevent diabetic retinal lesions is the most stable compensation of carbohydrate metabolism, normalization of systolic and diastolic pressure, correction of dyslipidemia with fenofibrate.